

NEW MEDIA, NEW NETWORKS: COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING IN RURAL WHATSAPP GROUPS - A CASE STUDY OF THE 'FEELGOOD' GROUP**Pallavi Singh Chauhan**

Research Scholar, Department of Mass Communication, School of Humanities & Social Science, Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India

Dr. Arti BhattAssistant Professor, Department of Mass Communication, School of Humanities & Social Science, Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India

ABSTRACT:

The rapid growth of social media platforms has transformed the ways in which individuals and communities share information. This paper investigates how new media platforms, particularly WhatsApp, facilitate the sharing of agricultural knowledge and foster community engagement among rural communities in Uttarakhand, India. Focusing on the FeelGood WhatsApp Group, a community of farmers dedicated to discussions on agricultural practices, migration, local news and community concern. This research adopts a qualitative approach to analyse how new media technologies are utilized for rural development. Through content analysis of the group's conversations, the study examines the dynamics of information exchange, the active participation of members and the role of WhatsApp in addressing local issues. The study also tries to explore the potential for both the spread of accurate knowledge and the dissemination of misinformation.

Key Words: Social Media, WhatsApp, Agriculture, New Media, Rural Development**INTRODUCTION TO NEW MEDIA AND NETWORKS**

In recent years, the advent of new media has significantly transformed the landscape of communication and development, particularly in rural areas. Unlike traditional media, new media platforms offer interactive and instant means of communication, enabling communities to access information, share knowledge and engage in discussions regardless of geographic limitations.

The emergence of new media technologies, particularly interactive social messaging platforms like WhatsApp, revolutionized how people access and share information in the 21st century¹ (**Chowdhury & Gow, 2024**). These digital platforms have become ubiquitous communication tools, fundamentally transforming the ways in which individuals, communities and organizations exchange knowledge, ideas and engage with one another² (**Pang & Woo, 2020**).

OBJECTIVE

This paper aims to examine the role of WhatsApp in facilitating agricultural knowledge sharing and community engagement among rural communities in Uttarakhand, India. This study analyses the content and dynamics of the FeelGood WhatsApp Group to investigate how new media technologies are leveraged for rural development. It examines the potential for disseminating both accurate information and misinformation, the preferred communication modes and the nature of messages shared, as well as the implications for community-driven knowledge exchange.

OVERVIEW OF THE FEELGOOD WHATSAPP GROUP

The Foundation: Sudheer Sundriyal founded the FeelGood WhatsApp group in 2016 after returning to his native village in Pauri, Uttarakhand, following years of residence in Delhi. Motivated by his strong connection to the region and a desire to support the local community, Sundriyal experimented with various agricultural and horticultural techniques. He engaged with other successful farmers and entrepreneurs in the area to further his efforts. The FeelGood WhatsApp group was established as a collaborative platform to facilitate knowledge exchange among agricultural practitioners. The group's name, "*FeelGood*", which translates to "*Bhalu Lagad*" in the Garhwali language, reflects the group's mission to create a supportive and enriching environment for its members³ (Singh, 2023).

The Journey: Since its inception, the FeelGood WhatsApp group has evolved into a vibrant digital community for farmers, agricultural enthusiasts and rural residents in Uttarakhand. This collaborative platform has facilitated the exchange of agricultural knowledge, fostered innovation and supported local farmers. The group's collaborative learning has helped members address challenges and adopt sustainable practices, ultimately enhancing their livelihoods and strengthening rural ties.

THEORETICAL INSIGHTS INTO WHATSAPP USE

WhatsApp, one of the most popular new media platforms, has emerged as a powerful tool for rural communities to share information and engage with one another. These communities find WhatsApp's features, such as instant messaging, group chats and multimedia sharing, particularly appealing to collaborate, access information and address local concerns⁴ (Resende et al., 2019).

Recent studies have highlighted the transformative role of WhatsApp in various aspects of rural life, including agricultural knowledge exchange, marketing and collective action⁵ (Naruka et al., 2017).

The study titled '**Social networking of innovative farmers through WhatsApp messenger for learning exchange: A study of content sharing**' discuss how WhatsApp groups facilitate the sharing of agricultural knowledge, best practices and community engagement among farmers. The simplicity and accessibility of WhatsApp make it an effective tool for fostering social cohesion and encouraging active participation in discussions about local challenges and aspirations, particularly in areas where digital literacy and resources may be limited⁶ (Nain et al., 2019).

The study draws on the theoretical frameworks of diffusion of innovations, uses and gratification and participatory communication approaches to examine the dynamics of knowledge exchange within the FeelGood WhatsApp group.

DIFFUSION OF INNOVATIONS

The diffusion of innovations theory helps explain how new ideas, technologies and practices are adopted and spread in a community⁷ (Rogers, 2015). The FeelGood WhatsApp group serves as a digital platform that enables the dissemination, experimentation and adoption of innovative agricultural practices and techniques among participating farmers, in line with the diffusion of innovations theory.

USES AND GRATIFICATIONS THEORY

The Uses and Gratifications Theory offers key insights into the reasons rural communities choose to use and engage with digital communication platforms such as WhatsApp. The

theory suggests that individuals actively choose media to meet specific needs, such as seeking information, engaging socially and seeking entertainment⁸ (**Katz et al., 1973**).

In the FeelGood WhatsApp group, farmers and community members use the platform primarily to acquire agricultural knowledge, stay informed on local news and connect with fellow farmers. The group's ability to fulfil these needs, such as providing access to reliable and context-specific information, enabling timely feedback and connections with peers and experts, has contributed to its sustained participation and growth. This empowers smallholder farmers by enhancing their agricultural extension and knowledge exchange within the rural community.

Digital communication platforms like WhatsApp empower smallholder farmers by providing access to reliable, context-specific information and enabling timely feedback, connections with peers and experts. These features position WhatsApp as a vital tool for enhancing agricultural extension and knowledge exchange within rural communities⁹ (**Thakur et al., 2017**).

The role and effectiveness of WhatsApp is further highlighted in the paper titled '*Effectiveness of WhatsApp Messages on Knowledge Gain of Sugarcane Cultivation Practices among the Farmers*', which demonstrates its significant impact on enhancing knowledge gain among sugarcane farmers. WhatsApp messages help share important farming information, connecting farmers and agricultural extension services¹⁰ (**Pawar et al., 2023**).

PARTICIPATORY COMMUNICATION APPROACH

The participatory approach encourages everyone in the community to communicate and work together on development projects. This is different from traditional top-down methods, where only experts make decisions. The participatory approach values the active involvement of community members in the decision-making process.

'Participatory Communication: A Practical Guide' highlights that participatory communication fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment, which is crucial for sustainable development. The FeelGood WhatsApp group embodies this approach by allowing its members to share knowledge, voice concerns and collectively address agricultural challenges¹¹ (**Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009**). Studies on various similar groups, such as the KVK (Krishi Vigyan Kendra) WhatsApp Group in Villupuram district, highlight the role of participatory communication in agricultural extension. These platforms enable real-time interactions among agriculturalists and experts, fostering knowledge sharing and enhancing decision-making¹² (**Narayanan & Senthilkumar, 2021**).

The theories in this review help us understand the FeelGood WhatsApp group. They show why members join, how the group spreads farming practices and the value of community-based communication for sustainable development. These theories guide the study's approach and analysis of how digital platforms can change how rural knowledge is shared and communities engage.

CONNECTING FARMERS: THE ROLE OF WHATSAPP IN RURAL KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE

Digital communication platforms like WhatsApp have changed how agricultural knowledge is shared in rural areas. Farmers turn to WhatsApp groups for agricultural communication and information exchange due to the following features offered through the platform:

- **User-friendly interface:** Facilitates easy access and navigation for all users, including those with limited digital skills.

- **Multimedia capabilities:** Allows sharing of diverse content, including text, images and videos, enriching the communication experience.
- **Real-time interactions:** Enables immediate communication, fostering timely discussions and responses among members.
- **Informal setting:** Creates a sense of community, encouraging farmers to seek advice and share personal experiences without hesitation.
- **Timely feedback:** Provides quick responses to inquiries, addressing the limitations of traditional extension services.
- **Personalized support:** Allows for tailored advice from peers and experts, enhancing the relevance of the information shared.
- **Peer and expert connections:** Facilitates networking among farmers, agricultural specialists, and local resources, improving knowledge sharing.
- **Enhanced collaboration:** Encourages cooperative problem-solving and sharing of best practices within the farming community.

Overall, these features position WhatsApp as a vital tool for enhancing agricultural extension and empowering smallholder farmers effectively.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research design, focusing on interviews and content analysis to explore the role of the FeelGood WhatsApp group. The primary data sources include an in-depth interview with the group's founder and a thematic analysis of discussions within the group.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLE AREA

The sample for this research includes participants from the FeelGood WhatsApp Group, which operates in Village *Chamnau*, Block Pokhra, in Pauri Garhwal district of Uttarakhand. This group is chosen as a representative case study to explore community engagement and the influence of new media technologies in rural settings.

The group, consisting of 261 members, was selected for its focus on sharing agricultural knowledge, which aligns with the study's objective of understanding the role of new media in rural development.

DATA COLLECTION

The study conducted a thematic analysis of the group's discussions from September 21 to October 22, 2024, categorizing topics such as agriculture and community. Additionally, an interview with the group's founder provided contextual information about its purpose and challenges, which enhanced the understanding of its role in facilitating rural knowledge sharing.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

In order to streamline the thematic frequency analysis, multiple related themes were grouped under broader categories for a clearer and more organised understanding. This grouping approach helped consolidate overlapping themes, providing a more organised view of the data while preserving the context and focus of each discussion.

Following is the thematic frequency table along with explanations for each grouped theme.

Table I / Grouped Thematic Frequency- Table

Broader Theme	Included Sub-Themes	Frequency
<i>Agriculture & Rural Economy</i>	Agricultural Success, Agricultural Challenges, Agricultural Standards, Farming and Economy, Challenges, Productivity	57
<i>Community Engagement</i>	Community Support, Community Development, Community Interaction, Community Responsibility	41
<i>Environmental Awareness</i>	Environmental Initiatives, Waste Reduction, Pollution Awareness, Water Resource Management, Environmental Degradation	19
<i>Societal Issues</i>	Societal Change, Societal Norms, Gender Dynamics, Marriage Dynamics, Economic Pressure, Social Etiquette	12
<i>Health & Wellness</i>	Health and Nutrition, Public Health, Health and Well-being	6
<i>Education & Employment</i>	Educational Disparity, Education & Employment, Employment Opportunities, Skill Training Programs, Male Unemployment	21
<i>Governance & Accountability</i>	Government Accountability, Critique of Governance Policies, Social Responsibility, Political Participation	7
<i>Cultural Identity & Preservation</i>	Cultural Identity, Cultural Dynamics, Tradition and Environment, Cultural Heritage and Promotion	18
<i>Social media & Misinformation</i>	Role of social media, Impact of Misinformation, Social Media Usage, Misinformation and Agriculture	5
<i>Economic Concerns</i>	Economic Inequality, Economic Empowerment, Employment, Economic Disparity	23

ANALYSIS

The study's key findings are organised into several core themes, each offering insights relevant to the overall research objectives (*Figure 1*):

- 1. Agriculture & Rural Economy:** With a frequency of 57, this theme encompasses various challenges and successes related to agriculture. It includes topics on productivity, economic dependency on farming and the standards and challenges faced by the agricultural sector. This theme is integral to understanding the rural economy and the community's reliance on agriculture for livelihood. The group also shares messages to provide information on successful agricultural techniques that can help yield good produce.
- 2. Community Engagement:** The most frequently occurring theme (frequency of 41) captures topics related to community support, development, interaction and responsibility. This theme shows how rural communities work together, demonstrating a strong bond and willingness to help each other. Community engagement is key for implementing social programs and getting people involved in development efforts.
- 3. Environmental Awareness:** Environmental issues are a significant part of the community's discourse, reflecting growing awareness and activism around concerns like degradation, pollution, waste and water challenges. The community focuses on preserving

local resources. The community has established plastic recycling programs in schools and community centres, a key focus in their environmental discussions.

4. **Societal Issues:** This theme addresses the social structures and challenges faced by individuals within the community, covering topics such as societal norms, gender dynamics, marriage expectations and economic pressures. The presence of these issues highlights the complexities of evolving social expectations in rural settings.
5. **Health & Wellness:** The health and wellness theme, with a frequency of 6, highlights important concerns such as nutrition, public health and overall well-being. These factors are essential for sustainable community development, as they directly impact productivity, quality of life and the economic stability of the region.
6. **Education & Employment:** This theme summarizes the community's concerns about educational disparities, limited employment opportunities and the need for skill development. With a frequency of 21, it highlights the importance of improving access to quality education and employment to reduce poverty and enhance socio-economic conditions.
7. **Governance & Accountability:** This theme addresses the community's engagement with governance, with a frequency of 7. It covers topics related to government, policies and programmes, etc. indicating the community's active interest on topics that impact their rural lives.
8. **Cultural Identity & Preservation:** This theme with a frequency of 18, highlights the community's efforts to preserve its cultural identity and traditions. The group aims to preserve its cultural heritage, upholding local values and practices despite broader societal changes.
9. **Social media & Misinformation:** This theme highlights the community's experiences with new media, including discussions on the impact of misinformation and the role of social media. The frequency of this theme is 5 which is low. This suggests the challenges of digital engagement and lack of digital awareness in the rural areas.
10. **Economic Concerns:** This theme with a frequency of 23 examines the community's economic challenges, such as inequality, employment issues and financial instability, highlighting the need for economic empowerment and sustainable development initiatives.

The thematic analysis offers a comprehensive overview of the rural community's key priorities and challenges. By grouping related themes, the analysis provides a clearer understanding of community dynamics and enables more targeted recommendations for development initiatives.

Figure 1| Theme-Based Distribution of Messages in the FeelGood WhatsApp Group

Analysis of Message Patterns across Different Categories

The analysis of message patterns in the FeelGood WhatsApp group provides important insights into community engagement and information sharing.

Message Category	Number of Messages	Percentage
Informative	139	36.8
Interactive	121	32.0
Community Support	62	16.4
Promotional	56	14.8
Total	378	100.0

Key patterns include:

- **Informational messages (36.8%):** Covering agricultural practices, market trends, and government schemes
- **Interactive messages (32%):** Fostering dialogue and mutual learning
- **Community support messages (16.4%):** Building emotional connections and a sense of belonging
- **Promotional messages (14.8%):** Effectively using visuals to advertise local products and services

Figure 2 | Category-Based Distribution of Messages in the FeelGood WhatsApp Group

Overall, the group's communication emphasizes informative, interactive, supportive, and promotional elements, with visuals playing a key role in enhancing engagement and knowledge exchange.

Analysis of Message Patterns by Content Type

The analysis of message patterns across different content types within the FeelGood WhatsApp group reveals several commonly used communication formats. The patterns of content type use suggest the preferred methods for sharing information, fostering interactions and supporting the group's objectives.

Here's a breakdown of each content type (Table III), along with observations about its use and significance within the group.

Frequency Grading Criteria

The frequency of each content type in Table III is categorized as follows:

- **Very High (5):** 30% or more of total messages; serves as a primary communication format.
- **High (4):** 20-29% of messages; plays a major role in engagement and information sharing.
- **Moderate (3):** 10-19% of messages; appears periodically, fulfilling specific functions.
- **Low (2):** 1-9% of messages; used infrequently for specialized or detailed content.
- **Very Low (1):** Less than 1% of messages; rarely used, typically for niche or dense information.

This grading system clarifies the role and importance of each content type in supporting effective group communication and engagement.

Table III | Message Patterns by Content Type in the FeelGood WhatsApp Group

<i>S. No.</i>	Content Format	Frequency	Purpose	Impact & Engagement
1	Images	High	Visual illustration of agricultural practices, community events	High engagement; easily grabs attention, simplifies complex ideas, effective in rural settings
2	Videos	Low	Tutorials, interviews, motivational clips related to agriculture, social issues	Provides depth and context; effective for educational content, though reach may be limited by data constraints
3	Social Media Posts	Moderate	Connect group with broader social issues, share government policies	Lends credibility through external sources; prompts discussions on broader social and community issues
4	Weblinks	High	Directs members to articles, reports, government portals	Useful for accessing detailed information but requires data and willingness to click through
5	Text-only Messages	Very High	Updates, community support, interactive discussions, calls for action	Flexible, accessible for all members; primary tool for fostering community support and group interaction
6	Audio Messages	Low	Detailed explanations, personal experiences	Adds a personal touch; useful for verbal communication but time-consuming to listen to
7	Documents/PDFs	Very Low	Distributing detailed reports, guidelines, or manuals	Highly informative but dense; valuable for those seeking in-depth information

Frequency Conversion and Calculations

To analyse the frequency distribution of content types in the FeelGood WhatsApp Group, qualitative descriptors were converted into numerical values (*From Frequency Grading Criteria*), and their percentages were calculated as follows:

Table IV | Frequency Distribution of Content Formats in the FeelGood WhatsApp Group

<i>Content Format</i>	Frequency Descriptor	Numerical Value	Percentage (%)
<i>Images</i>	High	4	19.05
<i>Videos</i>	Low	2	9.52
<i>Social Media Posts</i>	Moderate	3	14.29
<i>Weblinks</i>	High	4	19.05
<i>Text-only Messages</i>	Very High	5	23.81
<i>Audio Messages</i>	Low	2	9.52
<i>Documents/PDFs</i>	Very Low	1	4.76
Total		21	100

Figure 3| Frequency Distribution of Content Types in the FeelGood WhatsApp Group

Message Count Discrepancies: Analysing Classification Criteria

There appears to be a discrepancy between the total number of messages in the data set and the sum of the counts for each content type. This includes various content elements, such as emojis, reactions, repetitive messages and common responses. Additionally, some messages may fit multiple categories, contributing to variations. Discrepancies in message counts may arise from:

1. Different Counting Criteria:

- Grouped themes omitted duplicates.

- Content type (Image, Video, Text, Links, etc.) analysis included all message types, leading to higher counts.
2. **Message Overlaps:** Messages fitting multiple categories may have caused variations.
 3. **Inclusion/Exclusion of Media:** Deleted/media messages may be counted differently.

Summary of Findings: The analysis suggests that the different content formats used in the group serve distinct purposes.

- **Images and Videos** enhance visual understanding and engagement.
- **Social Media Posts and Weblinks** connect members to broader discussions beyond the group.
- **Text Messages** are the backbone of group communication, fostering interaction and community support.
- **Audio Messages** personalize communication and Documents/PDFs offer in-depth resources.

Each content type contributes to the group's collective knowledge, interaction and support, allowing for a dynamic flow of information and a balanced mix of accessible and detailed content. This diversity helps the group address varied needs, from quick updates and engaging visuals to comprehensive resources and interactive discussions.

ADDITIONAL KEY HIGHLIGHTS FROM FOUNDER CONVERSATIONS

The conversations with the founder provided insights into some other key highlights:

- Spam and Greeting messages are actively moderated by the group admin, maintaining a focused discussion space.
- The group also does not restrict the usage of local Garhwali language along with Hindi to allow all members to express themselves comfortably.
- Success stories of fellow farmers or even from different areas are shared and appreciated.
- Regular digital literacy workshops are organised to build the capacity of less tech-savvy members, empowering them to engage with the group more effectively.
- The group founder along with some experts and the moderators came up with an idea of publishing a monthly e-newsletter covering the key discussions and learnings from the group. This was named—*WhatsAppVaani*.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study underscore the profound capacity of community-based groups like the FeelGood WhatsApp group. This is particularly impactful in rural and remote areas, where conventional sources of information and assistance may be limited, making these groups essential for bridging gaps in access and fostering a stronger, more informed community. As digital technologies continue to transform information landscapes, harnessing the potential of such community-driven initiatives can unlock new pathways for inclusive and sustainable development in underserved regions.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The study offers several recommendations to enhance the impact of the FeelGood WhatsApp group and similar community-driven initiatives:

1. Establish a content-sharing schedule to maintain focus and organization.
2. Curate a shared resource library of images, videos and documents for easy access.
3. Enhance the frequency of expert-led Q&A sessions to address members' queries and concerns.
4. Implement regular feedback mechanisms to gather member input and improve engagement.
5. Provide digital literacy training to empower less tech-savvy members.

Future research could explore the following directions:

- Comparative analysis of content patterns and engagement dynamics in similar agricultural WhatsApp groups.
- Investigation of the long-term impacts of such community-driven knowledge-sharing initiatives on farmer livelihoods and community development.
- Understanding the role of WhatsApp group moderators in shaping effective group dynamics and knowledge exchange.
- Exploring the potential of integrating WhatsApp-based communities with other digital agricultural platforms and extension services.
- Evaluating the effectiveness of targeted content-sharing strategies and their influence on farmer knowledge and adoption of agricultural practices.

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